

Rui González de Clavijo's "Diary of a Trip to the Palace of Amir Temür" is a Source of Study of Trade in Eastern Cities

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Abstract: in this article, through Rui González de Claviño's "Diary of a journey to the Court of Amir Temür", issues such as Samarkand's place in trade with Eastern cities were subjected to scientific analysis.

Keywords: de Clavixo, Samarkand, Amir Temur, embassy, trade, City, Palace, diary, Pearl, Yarn, Shop, trade rastasi, caravanserai.

Rui González de Clavijo, of Spanish descent, was at the court of Emir Temür of Sahibqiron in 1403-1406 as ambassador to Castile and León (Spain). He traveled for more than a year (may 22, 1403, summer 1404), reaching Samarkand, the capital of the Temür state. Clavijo, with his messenger Corps (13 men), passed through dozens of cities in the West and East. In his diary he brings interesting facts about the topography, weather, water resources, architectural monuments, population, Customs and Customs, and economy of these cities. In particular, the issues of urban participation in trade were the focus of Clavijo. Within the framework of a single article, it is impossible to scientifically analyze the information contained in The "Diary". We want to give an idea of the facts and figures presented about some cities, important realities. Section 82 of the "diary" "is about the description of the city of Tabriz; " various things are sold on the most orasta streets and narrow streets of the city. There are well-built shops on the streets. Between the streets and narrow streets there were buildings with many doors that looked like castles, inside which cozy shops were located. Gates were opened from the building towards the streets. Sandals, taffeta silk, yarn, silk and pearls are sold on these streets-writes Clavicho. The author of the diary writes that Tabriz is a bustling, crowded trading city. With a population of more than two hundred thousand households, it is important that in this city (early 15th century) there are separate stalls selling perfumes, ointments for women, in which women come and trade on their own. The presence of mosques, madrasas, ponds and Wells in Tabriz , as well as caravanserai, aliens inhabited by foreign merchants, is curiously told in The "Diary". In Tabriz, Sultonia, Kabul, Andkhoy, Damascus, Mashhad, merchants, ambassadors and tourists stopped and built large buildings (rabort) for foreigners, where up to 50, 100, 200 horses were kept, which the ambassador consistently stated that it was intended to ensure the arrival of tulpors to Samarkand, the capital of the Timur state. Writing about the involvement of the city of sultonia in domestic and foreign trade, the Spanish ambassador said: "every year many merchants come here from Little India (Afghanistan). They bring to the Sultanate the freshest varieties of small fragrant fruits and medicines, peppermint, nutmeg, cinnamon, flour, nutmeg dye and other medicines that cannot be taken to Syria and Alexandria"[1]. It is also noted that silk was brought to the Sultanate from Baku (Azerbaijan) Guyelon (Northern Province of Iran), Shoi were sent to Damascus, Turkish cities from Sultania brought from Shamakha, Baku, Guyelon, Genoese and Venetian (Italian) merchants came to the Sultonian markets to buy silk. While spices such as

taffeta, sandalwood were brought to the city from Sheroz, yarns and non-spinning threads, various dresses were brought from Khuroson.

Clavijo: "the best Ruby, many sweets and medicines that will only be in China, will be brought here (Sultaniya) and then taken to other lands of the world. Giving a pearl polish is high in the Rooster. Muslim and Christian merchants say:" there is nowhere else but a rooster, which carves pearls and polished them." In the rooster, the Pearl is called "yasares", while being taken from the shells of white and large – large marine molluscs" [2] – he writes. When Yohud, González de Clavijo arrives in the city of Nishopur, it witnesses the presence of abundant, dairy, cream and bakery shops in the city's markets, and the bisection of the meat, fruit, melon markets. In every city where the spill occurred, ambassadors were presented with a wreath and one vulture horse by the administrators. "Nishopur, an omnipotent large city, is the ancient capital of Mideia. Nishopur is mined for feruza, which is of the highest quality compared to other lands. Here, feruzas are mined underground at a given location, as well as from a stream flowing from a mountain next to the city." [3] Clavijo wrote. Gomes de Salazar, a companion of González de Clavijo, had fallen ill and died in Nishopur. "Mr. molozim (a member of the local government) made a bell that night and laid Gomes, who was so weakened that he could not walk, and brought him to Nishopur, with people alternately raising him on his shoulders. Having placed Gomez in a very good building, they brought healers for treatment. It turns out that these healers are very good. However, according to the will of Allah, Gomes gave up his soul here." [4] in The "Diary".

Rui González de Clavijo's comments on the trade of the city of Samarkand, the capital of the Emir Temür dynasty, were written in many studies, so we bypassed it.

In conclusion, it would be appropriate to note that trade, crafts flourished in the cities under the reign of the Sahibqiron Amir Temur, where calm, calm, discipline prevailed. There is every reason to consider that such abundance and the spiritual potential of the population, as well as sincere, unique hospitality, surprised the ambassador of the Western country.

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